

Ballistic impact on composite-covered ceramic and the effect on projectile fragmentation

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Lightweight systems for personal ballistic protection

Carrier vest for soft insert
and hard armour plate

Hard armour plate

Helmet

Material combinations: ceramics, fibre composites, ballistic fibres, adhesives, ...

Important factors: Material properties, **weight**, **cost**, ...

How to combine different materials in the most optimal way?

Hard armour plate

Often designed to protect against armour piercing projectiles

7.62 mm APM2

How does it work?

- 1) The ceramic erodes and deforms the projectile – formation of smaller fragments
- 2) The restraint of the composite cover keeps the shattered ceramic together – important for multi-hit
- 3) The backing absorbs the residual kinetic energy – prevents complete perforation of the armour system

Purpose of the study

- Several studies have observed increased ballistic performance when the ceramic tile is covered with a sheet layer of a fibre-composite material (e.g. Sarva et al. 2007, Nunn et al. 2005, Reddy et al. 2008)
- Only small increases in areal density, i.e. little additional weight added
- The effects are mainly observed for composite covering on the front side of the ceramic, i.e. on the strike face, or on both sides of the ceramic
- Observed effects are:
 - More erosion/fragmentation of the projectile core
 - Lower residual velocity of core fragments after target perforation
 - Lower residual kinetic energy of core fragments
 - Higher resistance to perforation, i.e. higher V50
- Little comparison of front and back covers in the literature
- What is the effect for different configurations of ceramic/composite targets?

Composite-covered ceramic targets

Ceramic with two or four composite cover layers on front and/or back side

Ceramic

Alumina, 98% purity, tile size 8.2 mm × 100.1 mm × 100.1 mm (Alotec 98 SB, CeramTec, Germany)

Composite cover

Woven fabric of commingled glass and polyethylene terephthalate (PET) fibres (Comfil, Denmark)

↓ Melting and consolidation under heat and vacuum

Glass fibre/PET composite cover

Ballistic testing

Test procedure

- Projectile: 7.62 mm APM2 at 800 m/s
- The projectile fragments and other debris completely perforate the target
- All fragments collected with gelatine
 - mass of residual fragments
- High-speed video after perforation
 - velocity of residual fragments
- Residual kinetic energy of fragments can be calculated

Post-impact observation of targets

Target with
front cover

Target with
back cover

Target with
front and back cover

High-speed video

0.25 ms after impact

1.00 ms after impact

Velocity of largest residual projectile core fragment was measured – no significant difference between targets

Fragmentation of the 7.62 mm APM2 projectile steel core

Fragment size distribution

Tail fragments

Accumulated residual mass

Higher degree of projectile core fragmentation for targets with back cover

Kinetic energy of largest core fragment

Observations

- Kinetic energy of core prior to impact is 1665 J
- Kinetic energy of largest core fragment after perforation of targets with four composite cover layers:
 - With front cover 467 J
 - Bare alumina 394 J
 - With back cover 267 J
 - Up to 43% difference between targets
- Difference in mass contributes more than difference in velocity

Possible reasons for improved ballistic performance with back cover

- Difference in areal density can not alone explain improved ballistic performance
- The alumina will shatter when impacted
- Tensile cracks will originate on the back of the tile
- A composite cover will introduce some restraint on the back of the alumina
- Time-delay in the opening of tensile cracks
- Holds shattered alumina together
- More time for interaction between the projectile and the target
- Higher projectile erosion and fragmentation

Conclusions

- Two or four layers of a glass fibre-reinforced composite material were applied to the front and/or back side of alumina tiles
- Increase in areal density by no more than 9.5%
- After target perforation:
 - Up to 61% lower projectile core mass
 - Up to 84% lower kinetic energy
- Highest effect on ballistic performance observed for alumina targets with back cover
- Potentially easier to stop a projectile when the residual kinetic energy of fragments is low
- Increase in areal density cannot alone explain the improved ballistic performance
- Additional mechanisms are likely to be acting

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